

spiro-Compounds. Part I.

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Thorpe and his collaborators propounded their memorable "valency deflexion hypothesis" (Beesely, Ingold and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1080) on the basis of their exhaustive study of the relative ease of formation and stability of *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopropane* compounds and *gem*-dimethyl-*cyclopropane* compounds. But the difference in stability of the *spiro*-compounds (I) and (II) as observed by Birch and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1821) seems to be very strange in view of the said "valency deflexion hypothesis" and so the present author has undertaken the study of the formation and stability of different *spiro cyclobutane* derivatives analogous to norpinic acid, with a view to see whether the same kind of difference is to be observed in these cases also, and if so, to what extent could this phenomenon help to settle the question of a strained or strainless configuration of different ring systems.

If according to the suggestion of Sachse (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1363) and Mohr (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1918, ii, 98, 315) *cyclohexane* were to be a strainless ring then the ease of formation of these *spiro-cyclobutane* compounds would all be of the same order as *gem*-dimethyl compound such as norpinic acid (III) and its derivatives (Kerr, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 614) or else these should differ according to the difference observed by Thorpe and others between the behaviour of *cyclohexane* and other ring systems.

With this idea in view, the condensation of methylene iodide with sodio-derivatives of the Guareschi-compounds from *cyclohexanone* (IV) and other homologous ketones was effected according to the method of Kerr (*loc. cit.*). There was a possibility that the compound (V) could also be obtained in preference to the required product (VI) as it happens in methylating these Guareschi-imides (Kon and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1795) but fortunately the reaction went in the requisite direction yielding the *spiro*-compound (VI) where RR' are parts of different ring systems, *cyclopentane*, *cyclohexane* and substituted *cyclohexanes*.

The condensation products on being hydrolysed with alkali of different concentrations gave the compounds (VII), (VIII) and finally the tetracarboxylic acid (IX).

The tetracarboxylic acids of the type (IX) appear to behave rather in an anomalous way on being titrated with a solution of baryta, but on being heated to their melting temperatures these acids decompose with the loss of carbon dioxide and yield dicarboxylic acids of the type (X), which exist in both *cis*- and *trans*-configurations.* The silver salts of these tetracarboxylic acids decompose with explosive

* Their separation was effected by taking advantage of the fact that only the *cis*-acid forms an anhydride with acetyl chloride.

violence and so these experiments could not be relied upon but analysis gave results in complete accord with the tetracarboxylic acid structure. Such anomaly of behaviour on baryta titration has also been observed by Kerr (*loc. cit.*).

In conclusion the *spiro-cyclobutane* compounds described in the present paper have been found to correspond very closely to norpinic acid and its derivatives as regards their stability and ease of formation. The yield of the condensation product of methylene iodide with sodio-derivative of Guareschi-imide described in the present paper approximates very closely to that of dicyanonorpinimide of Kerr (*loc. cit.*) and the *spiro-cyclobutane* compounds have been found to be as stable as norpinic acid derivatives towards prolonged treatment with boiling caustic alkali. And moreover, these *spiro-cyclobutane* dicarboxylic acids lack remarkably in their tendency to crystallise, so much so, that some of them have not been obtained in crystalline condition, which reminds of the *spiro-cyclopropane* compounds derived from strain-free substances (Backer and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1579; Baker and Ingold, 1923, 123, 122). These facts in conjunction with an approximate similarity in stability of the substituted *cyclohexane spiro-cyclopropane* compounds and other *spiro-cyclopropane* compounds associated with strain-free substances (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1319; 1922, 121, 1823, etc.) strongly suggest the substituted *cyclohexane* ring to be strainless.

But a more conclusive proof of the strain-free character of substituted *cyclohexane* must be sought in the substituted *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane* and the corresponding *spiro-cyclohexane* compounds, the formation of which on the basis of the strain hypothesis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1980) is quite improbable, the effect of overlapping being of a very pronounced character (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 499) and so the author is engaged with the condensation of ethylene bromide and trimethylene bromide with Guareschi-compounds from cyclic ketones and the results already obtained appear to be of interest. These are reserved for a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Guareschi-imide with Methylene Iodide.—Guareschi-imide (1 mol.) was heated with sodium methoxide (3 mols.) in absolute methyl alcohol (1000 c.c.) under reflux on a water-bath for half an hour to yield the disodium derivative. To the

disodium derivative of the Guareschi-imide, methylene iodide (1.5 mols.) was added and the heating continued for 2-3 hours when almost the whole of methylene iodide dissolved and the reaction was complete. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into water (2000 c.c.) containing pure nitric acid (200 c.c.), when the condensation product was precipitated. It was then filtered, dried and washed repeatedly with ether to remove adhering methylene iodide and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. The yield of the condensation product varies from 60-65 p.c.

cyclopentane-1:1-spiro-dicycyclobutane Imide. [Formula VI, $RR'=(CH_2)_4<$].—Disodium derivative of the Guareschi-imide (10.8 g.) derived from *cyclopentanone* was condensed with methylene iodide (20 g.). It crystallises in needles from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 257°. (Found: N, 18.27. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 18.34 per cent.).

cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-dicycyclobutane Imide. [Formula VI, $RR'=(CH_2)_5$]. — Guareschi-imide (23 g.) from *cyclohexanone* was converted into its disodium derivative by treatment with sodium (6.9 g.) in absolute methyl alcohol (100 c.c.) and condensed with methylene iodide (40 g.), and the condensation product after usual treatment, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 266°. (Found: N, 17.42. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.28 per cent.).

4-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-dicycyclobutane Imide.—Disodium derivative of the Guareschi-imide (24.5 g.) from 4-methyl *cyclohexanone* was prepared and condensed with methylene iodide (40 g.) and the condensation product after preliminary purification crystallised from glacial acetic acid in needles, m.p. 252°. (Found: N, 16.3. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 16.34 per cent.).

3-Methylcyclohexane-1:1-spiro-dicycyclobutane Imide.—Methylene iodide (40 g.) and disodium derivative of Guareschi-imide from 3-methyl *cyclohexanone* (24.5 g.) were condensed in the usual way and the condensation product crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 259°. (Found: N, 16.3. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 16.34 per cent.).

Partial Hydrolysis of the Condensation Product of the type (VI). The condensation product (VI) (1 mol.) was dissolved in 10 p. c. potassium hydroxide solution (560 c.c.) and boiled for 5 minutes. The reaction product after cooling and extraction with ether to remove neutral product of reaction was acidified with hydro-

chloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was then washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, the bicarbonate-wash on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave the required acid of the type (VIII) as a thick oil which soon solidified and was crystallised from a suitable solvent (yield generally 80 p.c.).

cyclopentane-1:1-spiro-2':4'-dicyan-2'-carbamylicyclobutane-4'-carboxylic Acid. (Formula VIII, $RR' = (CH_2)_4 <$). —The condensation product (4.6 g.) was treated with 10 p.c. potassium hydroxide solution (11.5 c.c.) for 5 minutes, and the product of reaction after usual treatment crystallised from ethyl acetate in prismatic needles, m.p. 188°. (Found: N, 17.05 $C_{12}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N, 17 per cent.).

4-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-2':4'-dicyan-2' carbamyl-cyclobutane-4'-carboxylic Acid.

(Formula VIII, $RR' = MeCH < \begin{matrix} CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \\ CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \end{matrix} >$).

The condensation product (12.8 g.) was hydrolysed with 28 c.c. of 10 p.c. potassium hydroxide solution for 5 minutes and after preliminary purification crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 204°. (Found: N, 15.47. $C_{14}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N. 15.27 per cent.).

3-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-2':4'-dicyan-2'-carbamylicyclobutane-4'-carboxylic Acid. (Formula VIII, $RR' = -CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CHMe \cdot CH_2 -$). — 3-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-dicyanocyclobutane imide (12.8 g.) on hydrolysis with 10 p.c. caustic potash (28 c.c.) gave the required acid crystallisable in needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 211°. (Found: N, 15.49. $C_{14}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 15.27 per cent.).

cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane-2':4'-dicarbamyl-2':4'-dicarboxylic Acid. VII, $RR' = (CH_2)_5 <$.

cycloHexane-1:1-spiro-dicyanocyclobutane imide (VI) (12 g.) was dissolved in 2 p.c. caustic soda solution (200 c.c.) and boiled under reflux for 2 hours, when evolution of ammonia ceased. The reaction product was then cooled and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, when on stirring the acidified solution with a glass rod the required dicarbamyl dicarboxylic acid separated. It was then filtered, dried and crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 180° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.76. $C_{13}H_{18}O_6N_2$ requires N, 9.39 per cent.).

Complete Hydrolysis of (VII) and (VIII) to IX.—The compound (VII) or (VIII) was completely hydrolysed by boiling the same (1 mol.) with 20 p.c. sodium hydroxide solution (15-20 mols.), under reflux, on a sand-bath until evolution of ammonia ceased. The completion of the reaction generally takes 20-24 hrs. The reaction mixture was then cooled and acidified strongly with concentrated hydrochloric acid; suspended impurities removed by filtration and the filtrate extracted with ether many times. The ethereal extract on evaporation of ether gave the required tetracarboxylic acid as an oil which solidified on scratching with a glass rod, which was then crystallised from requisite solvent (yield 20 p.c.).

cycloPentane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane-2':2':4':4'-tetracarboxylic Acid [IX, $RR'=(CH_2)_4 <$].—*cycloPentane-1:1-spiro-2':4'-dicyanocyclobutane 2'-carbamyl-4'-carboxylic acid* (10 g.) was boiled under reflux with 20 p.c. caustic soda solution (200 c.c.) for 12 hours, and the tetracarboxylic acid separated as usual and crystallised from acetone and petroleum ether, m.p. 190° (decomp). (Found: C, 50.23; H, 5.12. $C_{12}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 50.35; H, 4.89 per cent.).

cycloHexane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane-2':2':4':4';-tetracarboxylic Acid [IX, $RR'=(CH_2)_5 <$].—*cycloHexane-1:1-spiro-2':4'-dicarbamyl cyclobutane-2':4' -dicarboxylic acid* (10 g.) was hydrolysed with a large excess of 20 p.c. sodium hydroxide as usual for 20-25 hours and the product was crystallised from acetone and petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 190° (decomp.). (Found: C, 51.59; H, 5.83. $C_{13}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 52.0; H, 5.33 per cent.).

4-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane-2':2':4':4'-tetracarboxylic Acid [IX, $RR'=\text{MeCH}(\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2)_2$].—*4-Methyl-cyclohexane 1:1-spiro-2':4'-dicyanocyclobutane-2-carbamyl-4'-carboxylic acid* requires 20-24 hours for complete hydrolysis. The product of hydrolysis

crystallised in needles from formic acid, m.p. 162°(decomp.). (Found: C, 53.18; H, 6.06. $C_{14}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 53.51; H, 5.73 per cent.).

3-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane-2':2':4':4'-tetracarboxylic Acid (IX, $RR' = -CH_2 - CH_2 - CH_2 \cdot CHMe - CH_2 -$).—*3-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-2':4'-dicyanocyclobutane-2'-carbonyl-4'-carbamyl* acid (10 g.) was hydrolysed in the usual way for 24 hours, the product of hydrolysis separated and crystallised from acetone and benzene in needles, m.p. 173°. (Found: C, 53.47; H, 6.28. $C_{14}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 53.51; H, 5.73 per cent.).

Decarboxylation of (IX) to (X).—The tetracarboxylic acid of the type (IX) was very cautiously heated in a large test tube in an oil-bath within 5° above the melting point of the tetracarboxylic acid so long as there was evolution of carbon dioxide, with stirring, care being taken that the contents of the test tube did not froth up above the surface of the oil-lench. When there was no more evolution of carbon dioxide the reaction product was cooled and dissolved in freshly distilled acetyl chloride and the acetyl chloride allowed to evaporate in the cold over caustic potash. The reaction product was then taken up in ether and washed twice with sodium bicarbonate solution. The ethereal solution on being dried and evaporated, yielded the anhydride of the *spiro-dicarboxylic acid (cis)*, as a thick oil. It solidified in a vacuum desiccator in course of time and was crystallised from proper solvent. The yield was very poor. The bicarbonate wash on acidification gave the *spiro-cyclobutane-trans-dicarboxylic acid* as a thick oil which was extracted with ether, dried and ether evaporated when the *trans-spiro-acid* was obtained as a gum which solidified in course of time when kept under reduced pressure over sulphuric acid, and crystallised from suitable solvent.

cycloHexane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane-2':4'-dicarboxylic Acid (trans) [X, $RR' = (CH_2)_5 <$].—The acid as obtained direct from the reaction product, is a gum and solidified after three days when kept in a desiccator under reduced pressure, and then crystallises in needles from ether, m.p. 178°. (Found: C, 61.9; H 7.74; equivalent, 108. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 62.27; H, 7.54 per cent.).

Anhydride of cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane-2':4'-dicarboxylic Acid (cis).—The anhydride solidified in the desiccator after two weeks, it crystallises from benzene in fine elongated needles, m.p. 159.62°. (Found: C, 68.13; H, 7.6. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 68.05; H, 7.21 per cent.).

Anhydride of 4-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane-2':4'-dicarboxylic Acid (cis).—The anhydride solidified in the desiccator after three months, and it crystallised from a mixture of ethylacetate and petroleum ether in short stout needles, m.p. 180°. (Found: C, 68.82; H, 7.75. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 19.23; H, 7.69 per cent.).

3-Methylcyclohexane-1:1-spiro-cyclobutane 2':4'-dicarboxylic Acid (trans). (X, $RR' = -CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CHMe \cdot CH_2 -$).—The acid solidified in a week and it crystallised from a mixture of acetone and petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 176°. (Found: C, 63.92; H, 7.93. $C_{12}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 63.72; H, 7.96 per cent.).

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